

MOIN4Herbie deliverable 7 - Expansion of existing equipment framework to sensor platforms

Authors: Mihir Rambhia (Hereon), Claas Faber (GEOMAR), Carsten Schirnack (GEOMAR), Fabian Kirchner (Hereon), Linda Baldewein (Hereon), Smruthishree Srinivasa (Hereon), Helmke Hepach (GEOMAR), Catriona Eschke (Hereon)

Publication date: April 30th, 2025

Figure 1: MOIN4Herbie logo

Introduction

Purpose

This document describes the expansion of the existing equipment framework to sensor platforms (Deliverable #7) for the MOIN4Herbie project. This project, funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), aims to integrate sensor maintenance ontology and audit logs into the Herbie electronic lab notebook (ELN). Deliverable #7 is part of Work Package 4, focused on expanding Herbie's capabilities by integrating it with existing sensor metadata registries.

Background

Sharing environmental observation data collected through monitoring stations, platforms, sensor networks, campaigns, and remote sensing is crucial for advancing scientific research, particularly in the Earth and environmental domains. In addition to observation data, sensor metadata provides essential context, helping researchers evaluate the relevance and quality of datasets. Public registries like the O2A Registry, Sensor Management System (SMS), and Persistent Identification of Instruments (PIDINST) are increasingly used to manage and share sensor metadata according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. Consequently, applications managing sensors often need to import metadata from these registries to operate effectively across different platforms.

The MOIN4Herbie project extends Herbie, a digital lab notebook designed for tracking scientific data provenance. A key goal is to digitize the storage of sensor maintenance metadata within Herbie. This requires accessing sensor details from registries such as the O2A Registry to plan maintenance and update sensor status.

To achieve this integration, the current work package developed Registry2RDF, a tool designed to transform data from the O2A Registry into the Resource Description Framework (RDF) format used by Herbie. This allows sensor metadata from external registries to be incorporated into the Herbie system, thereby expanding its capabilities. Accordingly, under the deliverable of expanding the existing equipment framework to sensor platforms, an existing sensor metadata registry is linked with the electronic lab notebook Herbie to digitize sensor maintenance activities.

Herbie: An Electronic Lab Notebook

Herbie is an electronic lab notebook platform built on a collaborative knowledge graph system, which uses an RDF triple store with features like versioning and access control. Users can upload RDF data, including vocabularies and SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) shapes for data validation.

The MOIN4Herbie project focuses specifically on storing sensor maintenance metadata within Herbie. To enable this, ontologies specific to sensor maintenance were developed and implemented using SHACL. This allows Herbie to validate user-provided maintenance metadata submitted as RDF graphs. However, while planning a maintenance activity, information related to the sensor platform, installed sensor type, manufacturer, owner, and location is necessary. Therefore, to enable the planning of maintenance activities, a crucial step is linking sensor metadata from registries like O2A with Herbie and updating sensor status information in the registry based on maintenance data.

Approach

To integrate O2A sensor metadata into Herbie, we established a connection using the O2A registry's RESTful Application Programming Interface (API). This API allows external applications, like Herbie, to request and retrieve metadata for specific sensors or platforms using unique identifiers (e.g., UUID, itemID). The registry returns this data in JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format.

However, Herbie uses RDF as its primary data model. RDF is a W3C standard for representing information as graph structures (subject-predicate-object triples), enabling semantic interoperability and linked data. While JSON is a standard response format, it lacks the structured semantics needed for direct integration

into RDF-based systems like Herbie. To comply with FAIR principles and support linked data integration, the JSON data must be converted into RDF triples. This conversion often involves using schemas like JSON-LD or mapping languages like RML.

To facilitate the format change, we developed the Registry2RDF module. This Python tool automates fetching metadata from the O2A registry API, transforming it into RDF, and saving it in a format that can be imported into Herbie. Accordingly, the module performs three main steps:

1. **Retrieves metadata:** Fetches JSON data for a specified sensor UUID or itemID from the O2A registry API.
2. **Maps data:** Maps JSON key-value pairs to semantic terms defined in the MOIN ontology using a specified JSON-LD context.
3. **Transforms data:** Converts the mapped data into Turtle (.ttl) format, a common RDF serialization, ready for import into Herbie.

Many observational platforms contain multiple sensors in a hierarchy. To handle these complex structures, Registry2RDF also includes a recursive feature. When given a parent platform's itemID, the tool identifies all child sensors within the hierarchy, collects their UUIDs, and then runs the Registry2RDF conversion process for each UUID. This ensures that metadata for the entire platform and all its sensors is converted into separate Turtle files.

Consultation with domain experts was conducted to finalize the list of metadata fields to extract, including decisions on whether to include detailed sensor parameters. Defining precise RDF property mappings for all selected fields is also essential for semantic accuracy.

In summary, integrating the O2A registry with Herbie involved connecting via the API, addressing the JSON-to-RDF data format mismatch, and using the Registry2RDF module to automate the metadata extraction and transformation process for individual sensors and complex hierarchies.

Registry2RDF Module

The Registry2RDF module is implemented as follows:

1. **Data Retrieval:** In the first step, sensor metadata is imported from the registry in JSON format. The script uses the `get_o2a_data(sensor_uuid)` function to request detailed metadata for a specific UUID from the O2A registry API endpoint (<https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/items/{uuid}>).
2. **Mapping:** In the second step, the relevant metadata is extracted from the retrieved data and mapped according to the MOIN ontology. To achieve this, the retrieved JSON data is processed by the `transform2moin_sensor(o2a_data)` function. This maps JSON fields (e.g., `shortName`, `description`) to semantic terms from the MOIN ontology (<http://purl.s.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/#>), such as `rdfs:label` and `rdfs:comment`. A predefined JSON-LD context (`get_herbie_context()`) guides this mapping and assigns the semantic type `moin:Sensor`. Additionally, adjustments are made during transformation to match RDF standards—for instance, correcting IRI references for sensor types.
3. **Transformation:** In the third step, the data is transformed into a compatible Turtle file. The `transform_sensor(o2a_sensor_uuid)` function carries out this process. It retrieves data, transforms it into a MOIN-compliant JSON-LD structure, parses this into an RDF graph using the `rdflib` library, binds the MOIN namespace prefix, and saves the graph in Turtle (.ttl) format along with the sensor name (e.g., `sensor1_data.ttl`).
4. **Recursive Loop:** The final step creates a recursive loop to deal with multiple sensors on a single platform and/or multiple platforms simultaneously. The three-step process for capturing the complete metadata for platforms with multiple sensors is as follows:
 - **Sensor Retrieval:** The script takes a parent itemID and fetches its full record, including nested children, from the API (https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/items/{item_id}?with=all).

Establishing the Link: O2A Registry API

A connection is established with Herbie using the O2A registry's API, which allows querying sensor or platform metadata by unique identifiers (UUID or itemID). The metadata is retrieved in JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format.

JSON ➡ RDF

Herbie relies on RDF (Resource Description Framework), but JSON lacks the semantic structure required. Therefore, JSON data needs to be converted to RDF.

Registry2RDF Module

- Retrieves metadata by UUID or itemID via API
- Transforms JSON to RDF by mapping to semantic fields and serializes to Turtle (.ttl) format
- Handles platforms with nested sensors recursively to ensure complete transformation of hierarchies

Figure 2: Approach
4

- **UUID Collection:** A recursive function (`collect_uuids` or similar) extracts the UUID (`@uuid`) from the parent record and traverses the `children` attribute to collect UUIDs of all descendant sensors.
- **Batch Conversion:** The script then calls the Registry2RDF tool as a separate process for each collected UUID, using `registry2rdf --item-uuid {uuid}`. This generates RDF data for every item in the hierarchy.

Repository

The Registry2RDF module has been developed in Python. The repository containing the code and documentation is available at: <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/moin4herbie/moin4herbie-public/-/tree/main/registry2rdf>

Discussion

The Registry2RDF module enables the integration of O2A registry metadata into Herbie. The developed module focused on extracting key fields necessary for identifying and organizing platforms, sensors, and parameters within Herbie, including names, serial numbers, descriptions, types, status, and units. Certain fields, like `status`, which represents states such as “public”, “devicestore”, or “decommissioned”, require consideration regarding how their representation in Herbie might be synchronized back to the registry after the maintenance activity is carried out. Therefore, while this initial version successfully transforms selected fields and handles hierarchies, further work is needed to link the registry’s edit capabilities using Herbie.

A broader challenge highlighted by this work is the lack of a standard method for integrating metadata across different sensor registries. Registry2RDF demonstrates an approach for one registry. If extended—perhaps using a unified SHACL shape applicable to various registries—it could contribute to a more standardized solution. This would benefit other applications needing to aggregate sensor data from multiple sources and aligns well with FAIR principles by converting registry-specific data into interoperable RDF graphs.

Conclusion

The MOIN4Herbie project developed the Registry2RDF module to connect the O2A sensor metadata registry with the Herbie electronic lab notebook. This tool retrieves sensor metadata via the O2A API, transforms the JSON data into a suitable Turtle file format, and exports it as RDF compatible with Herbie. Moreover, its recursive capability allows it to handle complex, hierarchical, and multiple sensor platforms effectively and simultaneously.

This development is an important step towards digitalizing sensor maintenance records by enabling the integration of standardized metadata from registries into Herbie. It demonstrates a potential pathway for standardizing metadata integration from diverse sensor registries, thereby improving interoperability and supporting FAIR data practices in the scientific community.

Sample Input JSON

```
{
  "@uuid": "05faafb9-0d85-4d7b-9a7d-47980c544655",
  "id": 12729,
  "created": "2025-03-12T08:47:28.289",
  "lastModified": "2025-03-12T08:48:13.613",
  "code": "mooring:box_gmr_twl-box_0924002",
  "shortName": "box_gmr_twl-box_0924002",
  "longName": "YTP Measurement Box",
  "description": "Measurement box transmitting data via LoRaWan, used with temperature and water level",
  "model": "TWL-Box",
```

```

"manufacturer": "Yachttechnik Pinck",
"serialNumber": "0924002",
"citation": "10013/registry.5662f2bf-2090-48d9-90b4-95debc6aa423",
"status": {
  "@uuid": "a080ff68-30b2-450a-9a44-06ecd244c0b7",
  "id": 1,
  "lastModified": "2020-11-18T09:14:53.011",
  "name": "public",
  "meta": "Item is completely described and operational."
},
"type": {
  "@uuid": "5fae2273-cc67-40b7-b99f-d4aeec864b20",
  "id": 44,
  "lastModified": "2020-11-18T09:46:30.379",
  "generalName": "mooring",
  "systemName": "mooring",
  "description": "A tethered collection of oceanographic instruments at a fixed location that may include",
  "vocabulary": "NERC",
  "vocableValue": "https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/48",
  "vocableGroup": {
    "@uuid": "85694c85-5aee-441f-a88a-a6bb8f1d0885",
    "id": 7,
    "created": "2024-09-04T09:04:10.581",
    "lastModified": "2024-09-06T13:19:29.361",
    "name": "DeviceTypes",
    "systemName": "DeviceTypes"
  }
},
"version": 0
}

```

Sample Output RDF

```

@prefix moin: <http://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/moin/#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .

<https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/items/05faafb9-0d85-4d7b-9a7d-47980c544655> a moin:Sensor ;
  rdfs:label "box_gmr_twl-box_0924002" ;
  moin:hasSensorType <https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/vocables/44> ;
  rdfs:comment ""Measurement box transmitting data via LoRaWan, used with temperature and water level
  Grauhoeft/Kappeln"" .

<https://registry.o2a-data.de/rest/v2/vocables/44> rdfs:label "mooring" ;
  rdfs:comment "A tethered collection of oceanographic instruments at a fixed location that may include" .

```